

Application of Chemical Reactions on Thin-Layer Chromatoplates. Part III—Peptides

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Most of the reactions achieved in this work were conducted with amino-acids and peptides. The reactions were performed on inert thin-layer chromatoplates under controlled conditions and the products of the reactions were compared as usual with the expected substances on the same chromatogram.

WE had mentioned in our previous work^{1,2}, that the application of chemical reactions on chromatoplates was developed to solve several problems, particularly in the field of natural products. The materials which the chemist can obtain from a natural source are in most cases too small to prepare derivatives for comparison with known products or to do reactions in the flask. For this reason we were interested to make this technique broad enough to involve other fields of natural products, to show which reactions proceed on chromatoplates.

Our aim in this work is to carry out some reactions on the amino-acids and peptides on the plates, in order to serve in widening the aspects of the technique and to overcome some difficulties encountered in our work on natural products.

Generally, the reaction is carried out by mixing the substance under examination mostly in solution form, with the reactions within the area of a small spot at the starting line of a plate of an inert adsorbent, such as silica gel. The mixture of reactants is then subjected to the favourable conditions and suitable length of time to simulate, as far as possible the normal reaction conditions in the flask. At the end of the reaction period a simplified "working up" may be necessary which is also performed within the confines of the spots. The absorbed layer is then treated in the normal manner as a chromatographic medium for the resolution of the components of the reaction mixture. Thus, development with a suitable solvent system enables the detection of the formed derivative and comparison with the expected material, spotted at the starting line immediately prior to development. Differentiation of the derivative from the starting material if any remains, is always possible if the appropriate conditions are used.

Results and Discussion

It appears that the application of the chemical reactions of amino-acid and peptides on an inert

chromatographic adsorbent, within the usual area of spot can produce results comparable to those obtained in conventional reaction apparatus.

Reactions which proceeded smoothly and the resulting compounds were obtained in good yields are :

1. Formation of (a) formyl amino acid³; (b) carbobenzoxy⁵ amino acid and (c) *o*-nitrophenylsulphonyl amino-acid⁶.
2. Removal of (a) formyl group⁴; (b) trifluoro acetyl group⁴; and (c) *o*-nitrophenylsulphonyl group⁶.
3. Dipeptide formation by (a) acid chloride method⁸, and (b) *p*-nitrophenylester method⁹.

While, reaction which proceeded with difficulty and the resulting compounds were obtained in poor yield are : (1) formation of trifluoro acetyl aminoacid⁴. (2) Removal of carbobenzoxy group⁵. (3) Formation of amino acid hydrazide⁷. (4) Dipeptide formation by (a) dicyclohexylcarbodiimide⁸ method; and (b) azide method⁷.

Experimental

Chromatoplates : These were prepared by the same procedure mentioned in reference 1. The development of the plates was achieved by placing them in a closed tank containing iodine.

General method for carrying the reactions on chromatoplates : The amino acid or peptide under examination in the appropriate solvent was applied on a plate at the starting line within the suitable reagents. The plate was placed in a closed desiccator saturated with the same solvent. After the time allowed was consumed under the suitable reaction condition, the plate was freed from the solvent prior to development. The results are listed in table 1.

TABLE I

Starting material (R_f)	Solvent	Time cons.	Reaction product (R_f)	develop. solvent* system
<i>Protection of amino group</i>				
Formyl amino acids				
Glycine (0.09)	AC ₂ O	1 hr.	Form. Gly-OH (0.7)	X
L-Leucine (0.11)	AC ₂ O	1 hr.	Form. L-Leu-OH (0.75..)	I
Trifluoro acetyl amino acids				
Glycine (0.10)	AC ₂ O	24 hr.	TFA-Gly-OH (0.55)	IX
DI-Alanine (0.15)	AC ₂ O	24 hr.	TAF-DI-Ala-OH (0.70)	II
Carbobenzoxy amino acids				
L-Valine (0.13)	NaOH	3 hr.	Z-L-Val-OH (0.56)	II
L-Leucine (0.12)	2N	3 hr.	Z-L-Leu-OH (0.69)	II
<i>o</i> -nitrophenyl sulphonyl amino acids				
Glycine (0.11)	NaOH	3 hr.	NPS-Gly-OH (0.45)	III
L-Asparagine (0.15)	2N	3 hr.	NPS-L-Asp(NH ₂)OH (0.57)	III
<i>Removal of protecting group</i>				
Removal of formyl group				
Form-Gly-Gly-OH (0.56)	dioxane	24 hr.	HCl-Gly-Gly-OH (0.71)	III
Form-L-Ala-Gly-OH (0.65)	"	"	HCl-L-Ala-Gly-OH (0.74)	III
Removal of trifluoroacetyl group				
TFA-Val-Gly-OH (0.74)	"	"	H-Val-Gly-OH (0.81)	IV
TFA-Gly-Val-OH (0.59)	"	"	H-Gly-Val-OH (0.66)	V
Removal of carbobenzoxy group				
Z-Gly-Gly-OH (0.50)	"	½ hr.	HBr-Gly-Gly-OH (0.71)	V
Z-Val-Val-OH (0.37)	"	½ hr.	HBr-Val-Val-OH (0.48)	V
Removal of <i>o</i> -nitrophenylsulphonyl group				
NPS-Leu-Gly-OH (0.41)	"	24 hr.	HCl-Leu-Gly NH ₂ (0.56)	VI
NPS-Gly-Gly-OH (0.39)	"	24 hr.	HCl-Gly-Gly-OH (0.59)	VI
Carbobenzoxy amino-acid hydrazide				
Z-Gly-OMe (0.21)	MeOH	1 hr.	Z-Gly-NHNH ₂ (0.20)	VII
Z-DL-Ala-OMe (0.32)	MeOH	1 hr.	Z-DL-Ala NHNH ₂ (0.35)	VII
<i>Dipeptide formation</i>				
Acid chloride method				
Z-Gly-Cl (0.65)	dioxane	24 hr.	Z-Gly-Gly OEt (0.54)	VIII
Dicyclohexylcarbodiimide method				
Z-DL-Ala-OH (0.76)	CHCl ₃	24 hr.	Z-DL-Ala-Gly OEt. (0.55)	VIII
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyloster method				
Z-Gly ONP (0.49)	dioxane	24 hr.	Z-Gly-DL-Ala-OEt (0.61)	VIII
Azide method				
Z-Leu-NHNH ₂ (0.41)	dioxane	24 hr.	Z-Leu-Gly-OEt. (0.69)	VIII

* Solvent system: I = ether-ethanol (4:1); II = ether-ethanol (2:1); III = ether-ethanol (9:1); IV = ether-methanol (7:3); V = benzene-ether (1:1); VI = ethereal; VII = ether-ethanol (3:2); VIII = benzene

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